

MAKERERE **UNIVERSITY**

**AWARENESS OF BILHARZIA AMONG FISHING COMMUNITIES
ALONG LAKE VICTORIA SHORELINE IN BUIKWE DISTRICT,
UGANDA**

BY

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**A RESEARCH REPORT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF SCIENCE,
TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION, IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT FOR
THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCE WITH EDUCATION DEGREE OF
MAKERERE UNIVERSITY**

NOVEMBER, 2019

DECLARATION

This research project is our original work and has not been presented for a degree or any other award in any other university or any other higher institution of learning.

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APPROVAL

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to our lovely parents, our lecturers and our friends who have always helped us in one way or the other throughout our education cycle.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Great thanks be to the almighty GOD for his abundant grace and faithfulness in all our academic achievements.

Special thanks go to our lovely parents who have given us support in everything both financially and socially providing all materials needed in our education.

We are grateful to our supervisor Dr. Allen Nalugwa of the Department of science, Technical and Vocational Education, School of Education, College of Education and External Studies, Makerere University.

Lastly, thanks to our friends, and the entire staff of the Department of science, Technical and Vocational Education, School of Education for their assistance and encouragement throughout this course

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ABSTRACT

Schistosomiasis commonly known as “snail fever” or “bilharzia” is a parasitic disease caused by blood flukes (trematode worms) of genus *Schistosoma* and affects hundreds of millions of people and accounts for more than 40% of the global health burden due to neglected tropical diseases. In Uganda, Schistosomiasis is endemic in 73 out of 121 districts and about 55% of the populations of 36 million individuals are at risk. This study investigated the awareness of transmission, symptoms and control of schistosomiasis among the people in Kiyindi fishing community in Buikwe district, one of the bilharzia endemic areas along Lake Victoria shoreline. A questionnaire was used to collect the necessary data and a total of 130 participants were included in the study. Findings show that 93.1% of the interviewees in Kiyindi landing site were aware of the existence and transmission of bilharzia in their community. About 77.7% of the entire communities were aware of the different symptoms of bilharzia and the majority (90%) were aware of the preventive measure of bilharzia. Although the majority of the people found in Kiyindi landing site were fully aware of the transmission of bilharzia in their community, only a few were aware of how the infection is acquired; many were not aware that bilharzia infection is through contact with infested water. Lake Victoria being the major source of water, Kiyindi fishing community living at the shoreline has continued to be at risk of bilharzia infection. This study recommends construction of more pit latrines in the community for proper sanitation disposal in order to intervene the spread of bilharzia parasites in the surrounding water. The community in Kiyindi landing site should also receive more sensitization about the transmission and control of bilharzia.

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 Background

Schistosomiasis commonly known as “snail fever” or “bilharzia” is a parasitic disease caused by blood flukes (trematode worms) of genus *Schistosoma* (World Health Organization, 2016). Transmission occurs when people suffering from bilharzia contaminate fresh water sources with excreta containing parasitic eggs which hatch in water (NHS.UK, 2016). Human infection occurs when cercariae released by freshwater snails penetrate skin during contact with infested water. Worldwide, about 700 million people are at risk of infection, with over 200 million people being infected in low to middle income countries (Ramadhan *et al*, 2016). Bilharzia is endemic in 74 countries and territories (World Bank, 1997). The morbidity caused by bilharzia is chronic and results in a huge socio-economic burden that is often underestimated (King *et al*, 2008). - Bilharzia can result in abdominal pain, diarrhea, and blood in the stool. Liver enlargement is common in advanced cases and is frequently associated with an accumulation of fluid in the peritoneal cavity and hypertension of abdominal blood vessels. In such cases there may also be enlargement of the spleen (WHO, 2018). The main schistosomes infecting human beings are; *Schistosoma mansoni* which are transmitted by *Biomphalaria* snails and causes intestinal and hepatic Schistosomiasis in Africa, the Arabian Peninsula, and South America. *Schistosoma haematobium*, transmitted by *Bulinus* snails causes urinary schistosomiasis in Africa and Arabian Peninsula, and *Schistosoma japonica* transmitted by the amphibian snail *Oncomelania* causes intestinal and hepatosplenic Schistosomiasis in China, the Philippines, and Indonesia. *Schistosoma intercalatum* and *Schistosoma mekongi* are only of local importance. *Schistosoma japonicum* is a zoonotic parasite which infects a wide range of animals including cattle, dogs, pigs, and rodents. (Bruno *et al.*, 2000).

Over 90% of all *Schistosoma* infections are found in sub-Saharan Africa (Sanya *et al*, 2017). Of Uganda's 121 districts, 73 have Schistosomiasis with about 55% of the population at risk. Estimated 4 million people are infected with infection rates varying widely from 92% in some areas to as little as 2% in others. It is not just a rural problem, either. One study found 65% prevalence in a district of Kampala, Uganda's capital city (Loewenberg, 2014). In Uganda, intestinal schistosomiasis caused by *Schistosoma mansoni* is the most common type and has been known for a long time on shores of Lakes Albert, Victoria and Kyoga and along the Albert

Nile (Kabatereine, *et al.*2014). Districts around Lake Kyoga have a 45% prevalence rate of bilharzia. (CEGET, 1987).

Buikwe district is found in Central Uganda and lies in Buganda sub-region. The district is bordered by Kayunga district to the North, Jinja district to the East, Buvuma Island to the Southeast, the Republic of Tanzania to the South and Mukono district to the West. Bilharzia has a prevalence of 24% in Buikwe district alongside, malaria, sleeping sickness, diarrhea and typhoid which have prevalence of 49%, 3%, 4% and 20% respectively(Ssebibusi, 2013).Preschool-aged children1–5 years on the northern Lake Victoria shoreline of Uganda are at high risk of intestinal schistosomiasis infection as much as are school-age children and adults. They get exposed to *S. mansoni* infested waters through bathing, playing or swimming. (Nalugwa, *et al.*, 2014). Following the 2001 World Health Assembly resolution 54.19 (WHO, 2002), Uganda initiated a national bilharzia and worm control programme in 2003 (Kabatereine *et al.*, 2007) that first targeted high- moderate transmission foci near large Lakes and along river Nile Following the 2001 World Health Assembly resolution 54.19 (WHO, 2002), Uganda initiated a national bilharzia and worm control programme in 2003 (Kabatereine *et al.*, 2007) that first targeted high-moderate transmission foci near large Lakes and along River Nile.

In Uganda, bilharzia control began in the early 1990s but it was insubstantial. It was boosted by financial support from the Schistosomiasis Control Initiative (SCI) in 2003 (Kabatereine, *et al.* 2006) targeting morbidity control through annual mass treatment (Fleming *et al.*2009). By 2006, the prevalence and intensity of infection in majority of the foci had been drastically reduced (Kabatereine, *et al.*,2007) and transmission interruption seemed potentially possible in majority of the affected areas. The United States Agency for International Development (USAID) through Research Triangle Institute (RTI) expanded the interventions by launching an integrated NTD control programme in 2007 targeting LF, bilharzia, trachoma, Onchocerciasis, and STH (Linehan, *et al.*, 2011).Currently, there is a need to assess the level of awareness of bilharzia among the fishing communities in Buikwe district such that it provides basis on the knowledge possessed by fishing communities about the cause, transmission and prevention of Bilharzia in order to reduce its morbidity and mortality by improving the level of awareness.

1.2 Problem statement

The prevalence of bilharzia is still high despite the routine mass interventions in Buikwe district and Uganda in general. This research project, therefore, seeks to investigate the awareness of bilharzia and its control among communities living along the Lake Victoria shoreline, in Buikwe district.

1.3 Justification

This study is needed to find out whether people are aware of the causes, symptoms, transmission, and prevention of bilharzia in order to reduce its morbidity and mortality in Buikwe district.

1.4 General aim of the study

To investigate awareness of bilharzia among fishing communities along Lake Victoria shoreline in Buikwe district, Uganda.

1.5 Specific objectives

1. To determine the level of awareness of transmission of bilharzia among fishing communities along Lake Victoria shoreline in Buikwe district.
2. To determine the level of awareness of the symptoms of bilharzia among fishing communities along Lake Victoria shoreline in Buikwe district, Uganda.
3. To determine the level of awareness of prevention and control of bilharzia among fishing communities along Lake Victoria shoreline in Buikwe district.

1.6 Research questions

- i. What is the level of awareness of Schistosomiasis in Buikwe district?
- ii. What activities are there in the community that creates awareness about intestinal schistosomiasis?
- iii. What are the control measures taken by the people in the fishing communities of Buikwe district to combat schistosomiasis?

1.7 Significance of research study

The findings from this research will throw more light to the fishing communities about the causes, transmission and prevention of bilharzia. They will also throw more light to the bilharzia prevention campaigns in the various bilharzia endemic communities in Uganda.

1.8 Scope of the study

The study will focus on people in the fishing communities i.e. fishermen, women and children.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Bilharzia

About 700 million people have a worldwide risk of infection with over 200 million people being infected in low to middle income countries. (Ramadhan *et al.*, 2016). In 2012, the disease affected 240 million people worldwide, mainly in tropical and sub-tropical regions (WHO, 2016). The world health organization estimated that at least 258 million people needed preventive treatment for schistosomiasis in 2014 and over 61.6 million people were treated for schistosomiasis in the same year (WHO, 2016). Different species of Bilharzia or schistosomiasis are found around the world. The main areas according to the CDC are; Southern, central, West and Sub-Saharan Africa in the great lakes and rivers, and in smaller bodies of water, the Nile river valley in Sudan and Egypt, and the Maghreb region of northern Africa. Brazil, Suriname, and Venezuela in South America, Indonesia, parts of China and South East Asia, including Cambodia and Laos, Middle East, Yemen in Asia.

Whereas a number of countries have managed to sustain bilharzia control over the last two decades, most donor-funded vertical control initiative set up in Africa during the 1980s have shown to be unsustainable. Despite the fact that the 1991 WHO expert committee on the control of bilharzia called for greater flexibility and a more prominent for primary health care services (PHC). (WHO, 1993) The disease registers high rates of morbidity, in about 20 million people and mortality about 280000 deaths annually, especially in tropical and sub-tropical countries. (Van Der Werfa *et al.*, 2003).

Globally, Africans carry 98% of the disease, and in some communities, as many as 50% of the population suffers. Bilharzia mostly prevalent in sub-Sahara Africa, where not only it overlaps with other few low priority diseases but also high priority diseases such as HIV, malaria, and tuberculosis. (Tarko *et al.*, 2013). Almost 300000 people die annually from bilharzia in Africa alone. Approximately 90% of the 250 million people infected worldwide live in sub-Saharan Africa where *Schistosoma mansoni* is the prevalent species. About 10 million women in Africa are infected during pregnancy. (Olveda *et al.*, 2013). Nigeria is the most endemic country for bilharzia with approximately 20 million people, mostly children needing

treatment. (The Carter Centre). In 2008, 17.5 million people were treated globally for bilharzia; 11.7 million of those treated were from sub-Saharan Africa. This enervating disease has been successfully eradicated in Tunisia. Morocco has made significant progress on control and management of this disease. Most travel-associated cases of schistosomiasis are acquired in sub-Saharan Africa; sites in Africa frequently visited by travelers are common sites of infection. These sites include rivers and water sources in the Banfora region (Burkina Faso) and areas populated by the Dogon people (Mali) Lake Malawi, Lake Tanganyika, Lake Victoria, the Omo River (Ethiopia) the Zambezi River and River Nile. However, as visitors travel to more uncommon sites it's important to remember that most fresh surface water sources in Africa are potentially contaminated and can be sources of infection. (CDC, 2015)

In Uganda, *Schistosoma mansoni* was first observed and reported in Kuluva hospital Arua District north western Uganda by Aldo Castellani and G.C Low in 1902; in a hospitalized patient with sleeping sickness (Odongo- Aginya *et al.*, 2008). In Uganda today, of 126 districts, Bilharzia is reported in 84 districts (Ministry of Health, 2018). Recent nationwide study shows Bilharzia prevalence at 29%, meaning one in every three persons has the disease. (New Vision, 2018). Districts around Lake Kyoga have a 45% prevalence rate of bilharzia. (CEGET, 1987). The ministry of health started mass drug administration exercise for prevention of bilharzia in 13 endemic districts on 18th April 2017. These districts include Ntoroko, Rubirizi, Koboko, Kamwenge, and Kiryandongo. Other districts include Mayuge, Buyende, Bugiri, and Namayingo in the eastern region (envision, 2017).

2.2 Life Cycle of Schistosome parasite and transmission of bilharzia

Bilharzia is caused by digenetic blood trematodes. The three main species infecting humans are *Schistosoma haematobium*, *Schistosoma japonicum*, and *Schistosoma mansoni*. Two other species, more localized geographically, are *Schistosoma mekongi* and *Schistosoma intercalatum*. In addition, other species of schistosomes, which parasitizes birds and mammals, can cause cercarial dermatitis in humans. (King *et al*, 2005). The eggs are eliminated with faeces or urine, under optimal conditions they hatch and release miracidia which swim and penetrate specific snail intermediate hosts (*Biomphalaria* snail species). Inside the snail, there is generation of sporocysts and production of the cercariae. Upon release from the snail, the infective cercariae swim, penetrate the skin of the human host and shed their forked tail, becoming the schistosomulae. The schistosomulae migrate through several tissues and stages to

their residence in the veins. Adult worms in humans reside in the mesenteric venules in various locations, which at times seem to be specific for each species.

Schistosoma japonicum and *Schistosoma mansoni* are more frequently found in the superior mesenteric veins draining the small intestine and large intestines respectively. However, both species can occupy either location, and they are capable of moving between sites, so it is not possible to state unequivocally that one species only occurs in one location. The females deposit eggs in the small venules of the portal and perivesical systems. The eggs are moved progressively toward the lumen of the intestine and are eliminated with faeces or urine respectively. Ultimately the adult worms migrate from the liver through the portal vein to the mesentery and the wall of the bowel. These adult worms do little damage to the host. They feed on circulating erythrocytes and plasma glucose but usually don't cause symptoms. (Wafa and King, 2009)

Infection is usually acquired through activities such as swimming, bathing, fishing, farming and washing clothes. Important transmission sites include Lake Malawi and Lake Victoria in Africa. (Gryseels *et al*, 2006) The host immune response to schistosome eggs is the hallmark of the disease due to the schistosomiasis, in that immunological reaction and granuloma formation in the tissue is responsible for morbidity and mortality of chronic schistosomiasis. (Wafa and King, 2009). Bilharzia is not transmitted by vectors. It affects communities that are in contact with water and poor sanitation brought about by people defecating in or near the water bodies (New vision, 2018)

2.3 Symptoms of Bilharzia

The symptoms of bilharzia depend on the type of worm and the stage of infection, but they are mostly the result of the body's reaction to the worms' eggs, and not caused by the worms themselves. Early symptoms are swimmer's itch, which include itchy skin and a rash. They may appear within hours of being infected, and they can last for up to around 7 days. Within another month or two a person who has been infected may experience fatigue, fever, chills, cough, muscle aches, abdominal pain, diarrhea, dysentery and blood in the urine. This phase coincides with the maturation of the worms in the body, and is called Katayama fever. (NHS.UK, 2016).

Approximately 3 to 8 weeks after infection, the person may experience: Fatigue, Fever and chills, Cough, Muscle aches, Weight loss, Enlargement of the liver and spleen, Diarrhoea,

Abdominal pain. These symptoms, known as acute Schistosomiasis, often get better by themselves within a few weeks. (CDC, 2012). Some people with schistosomiasis, regardless of whether they had any initial symptoms or not, eventually develop more serious problems in parts of the body the eggs have travelled to.

This is known as chronic schistosomiasis. Chronic schistosomiasis can include a range of symptoms and problems, depending on the exact area that's infected. For example, an infection in the: Digestive system can cause anemia, abdominal pain and swelling, diarrhea and blood in your faeces; Urinary system can cause irritation of the bladder (cystitis), pain when peeing, a frequent need to pee, and blood in your urine; Heart and lungs can cause a persistent cough, wheezing, shortness of breath and coughing up blood; Nervous system or brain can cause seizures (fits), headaches, weakness and numbness in your legs, and dizziness (NHS.UK, 2016). Without treatment, affected organs can become permanently damaged

Other symptoms include inflammation and scarring in the liver, bladder, and intestines. Children with repeated exposure to Schistosomiasis can develop anemia or malnutrition. Schistosomiasis can also lead to learning difficulties. If left untreated, Schistosomiasis can cause seizures or inflammation in the spinal cord. If the parasite eggs make their way to the brain or spinal cord, paralysis can occur. Children with bilharzia face developmental and intellectual challenges. Death can be a result of bilharzia. Treatment can help reverse some of these symptoms. (Health 24, 2015)

2.4 Diagnosis, treatment and control of bilharzia

2.4.1 Diagnosis

The microscopic examination of excreta remains the gold standard for the diagnosis of bilharzia. The eggs are easy to detect and identify by microscopy owing to their size and shape, their typical lateral or terminal spine, and the living miracidium (in fresh samples) with mobile cilia and pulsing excretory cells. Direct wet slides are not very sensitive; if no eggs are found, concentration methods should be used but even these can miss light infections. Urine should be concentrated by sedimentation, centrifugation, or filtration, and samples should be taken around noon or after physical exercise. To obtain a quantitative assessment of the intensity of infection, a fixed amount (generally 10 ml) of urine is forced over a paper or nitrocellulose filter, which can be examined and eggs counted directly under the microscope. Intensity can then be expressed as eggs per 10 ml.

For the intestinal schistosomes, eggs must be examined the faeces. Concentration methods, such as sedimentation in a glycerin solution or centrifugation in formalized ether are needed for detection of mild and light infections. In the field, the faecal thick smear or Kato-Katz method is commonly used, because it allows quantification of the infections by egg counts, usually expressed as per g faeces. Rectal snips are very sensitive, even for *Schistosoma haematobium* infection.

Quantitative egg counts after standardized urine filtration or in calibrated faecal thick smears are especially useful for epidemiological surveys and control, since they correlate well with worm burdens and morbidity. Individual egg counts should not be over interpreted as a measure of disease, however, because they vary substantially within and between stool and urine samples. If the patient has intestinal symptoms, they may need a biopsy of the rectum even if urine and bladder tests are negative. The patient may also have a bladder biopsy. (Health 24, 2015).

2.4.2 Treatment of bilharzia

Bilharzia can usually be treated with a short course of a medication called praziquantel, which kills the adult worms. It is active against all schistosome species, and is now the most widely used. It is mostly marketed as 600 mg tablets, Praziquantel, an acylated quinoline-pyrazine is most effective once the worms have grown a bit, so treatment may be delayed until eight weeks after you were infected, or repeated again after this time. With a recommended standard regimen of 40 mg/kg bodyweight in a single dose the drug acts within 1 hour of ingestion by paralyzing the worms and damaging the tegument. Side-effects are mild and include nausea, vomiting, malaise, and abdominal pain. (Gryseels *et al*, 2006). In heavy infections, acute colic with bloody diarrhea can occur shortly after treatment, probably provoked by massive worm shifts and antigen release.

Praziquantel has very low toxicity in animals, and not important long-term safety difficulties have been documented in people so far. It is judged safe for treatment of young children and pregnant women. Praziquantel has little or no effect on eggs and immature worms. Tissue-dwelling eggs can be excreted for several weeks after treatment, and during the same period prepatent or newly acquired infections can become productive. The preferred timing of follow-up is therefore 4–6 weeks after treatment. After a single dose of 40 mg/kg, 70–100% of patients cease to excrete eggs. (Gryseel *et al*, 2006). Other drugs include; Oxamniquine for

treating intestinal Bilharzia, Metrifonate for treating urinary Bilharzia and Artemisinin derivatives which are effective against the immature stages of *Schistosoma japonicum*, *Schistosoma mansoni*, and possibly *Schistosoma haematobium*.

2.4.3 Control and prevention of bilharzia

There is no vaccine for bilharzia, so it's important to be aware of the risks and take precautions to avoid exposure to contaminated water. You can check whether the area you are visiting is known to have a problem with bilharzia using Travel Health Pro's country information section. If you are visiting these areas; avoid pedaling, swimming, and washing in fresh water-only swim in the sea or chlorinated swimming pools. Take water proof trousers and boots with you if there is a chance you will need to cross a stream or river. Boil or filter water before drinking as the parasites could burrow into your lips or mouth if you drink contaminated water. Avoid medicine sold locally that are advised to prevent or treat schistosomiasis because these are often either is fake, substandard, ineffective or not given correct dosage. Don't rely on assurances from hotels, tourist boards or similar that a particular stretch of water is safe, there have been reports of some organizations downplaying the risks.(NHS.UK,2016) Applying insect repellent to your skin or quickly drying yourself with a towel after getting out of water aren't reliable ways of preventing the infection although it's a good idea to dry yourself as soon as possible if you are accidentally exposed to potentially contaminated water There's some evidence that applying insect repellent containing 50% DEET to exposed areas each night after showering kills the parasite in the skin before it moves deeper into the body(NHS.UK,2016). In some places, there are projects to eliminate the water dwelling snails that carry the disease. This can be done with acrolein, copper sulphate and nitrosamine. In other places introducing Cray fish to areas where the snails exist can help to control snail population. As with any ecological intervention this must be done with causation. (CDC, 2012)

2.8. Role of various stakeholders in controlling bilharzia in Uganda

National prevalence dropped to 20.4% in 2003 and to 15.9% in 2010 after initiation of the Schistosomiasis control initiative mass drug administration efforts from 2004 to 2008. (Lai Y. S, *et al*) In 2004, the Schistosomiasis control initiative national control programmes began operations in Uganda, with the support of the united states agency of international development (USAID) and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.(WHO, 2015) With the help of this program, mass drug treatment with praziquantel were scaled up in 2010 to 2012 with 2.66

million , 1.47 million, and 1.6 million people reportedly treated (a national coverage in Uganda of 33%, 18%, and 19%, respectively in 2010, 2011, and 2012)(Hotez, P.J. *et al*). Kampala 31st August, 2017, the ministry of health with support from partners convened in a two-day meeting to discuss control and elimination of Schistosomiasis (Bilharzia) in Uganda. The meeting provided an opportunity for the experts to review the details of the ministry of health's NTD programme implementation, coverage of the different interventions, possible reasons for the resurgence of Schistosomiasis and provide guidance on a comprehensive approach to controlling bilharzia, using the available tools. WHO coordinates the strategy of preventive chemotherapy in consultation with collaborating centers and partners from academic and research institutions, the private sector, nongovernmental organizations, international developmental agencies and other United Nations Agencies it further develops technical guidelines and tools for adaptation and use by national control programmes. The World Health Organization is also advocating for the integration of WASH interventions for elimination of NTD's by 2020. (WHO, 2017).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study area

Buikwe district is found in Central Uganda, bordered by Kayunga district to the North, Jinja district to the East, Buvuma Island to the Southeast, the Republic of Tanzania to the South and Mukono district to the West. The District lies within the coordinates 00021’N 33002’E. The main economic activities in the district are fishing and agriculture. Data will be collected at Kiyindi landing site in Najja sub-county.

Figure 1. A sketch map showing Lake Victoria shoreline fishing communities in Buikwe district.

3.2 Study design

The study will employ a cross-sectional survey and qualitative methods, including focus group discussions (FGDs) and key informant interviews (KIIs). The qualitative methods will be employed because the nature of the study requires ideas, views and perceptions of fishermen, children and their care givers in order to estimate their awareness about schistosomiasis and its preventive measures. FGDs will be conducted with community members to gauge community knowledge, attitudes and practices towards schistosomiasis control. KIIs will be conducted on opinion leaders on schistosomiasis its control in terms of water, sanitation and treatment.

3.3 Study population

The study population will comprise of fishermen, women and children from whom information relevant to the completion of the study will be obtained.

3.4 Sample size determination and selection

3.4.1 Sample size determination

The sample size was estimated using the formula below;

$$N = \frac{Z^2 * P(1 - P)}{C^2}$$

Where;

N is the total sample size

Z is the level of significance (Z-score is 1.96 at 95% confidence level)

P is percentage of picking the choice which is 50 (minimum value at 50%)

C is margin of error/ confidence interval at 9%

Thus;

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \frac{1.96^2 * 0.5(1 - 0.5)}{0.09^2} \\ &= 119 \end{aligned}$$

3.4.2 Sampling procedure

The study sampling will be both simple random and purposive. Simple random sampling will be employed to obtain a representative and manageable sample of the population due to the researchers' inability to reach all respondents in the target population. Purposive sampling will be used to select the good representation of the key informants and these will include; local leaders and health officers. These key informants will be selected owing to their knowledge and experience about the study topic. Fishermen, care givers and children will be selected using simple random sampling technique.

3.5 Data collection

The study will employ the use of well-structured questionnaires during the process of data collection. The questionnaires will be designed in such a way that the questions will be in line with the objectives of the study and will be both open-ended and closed-ended. The open-ended questionnaires will enable respondents to respond freely while the closed-ended will have predetermined responses that will make it easier for the researcher to analyze the data. The

instrument is preferred as it saves time and also relatively large number of respondents will be needed (Goodwin 2004, as cited in Harmer 2005). Also, the data collected using questionnaires is easy to analyze especially with use of the computer. The researchers will administer the questionnaires to the respondents and in cases where some are unable to reach, the researchers will read and interpret the questions to them in their local language so as to give the correct information.

3.6 Data Analysis

Since quantitative and qualitative data will be collected, the study will employ both quantitative and qualitative methods of data analysis respectively. However, the study being mostly descriptive in nature, the researchers mostly will employ the qualitative method. The data collected through questionnaires and interview guides will be edited so that uniformity, legibility, accuracy and consistency are checked and errors of omission are eliminated. The data will then be coded and entered into the computer and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) version 16. The package will be used because it has the capacity to accommodate a large number of variables at the same time. Qualitative data analysis will involve use of descriptive statistics. This will be in form of frequencies presented in tables. Qualitative data analysis and presentation will involve a narrative analysis of data to enrich the study with real and vivid information as will be given by respondents.

3.7 Ethical considerations

Consent will be obtained from the participants and confidentiality will be ensured as the information collected will be used for research purposes. Each participant will be given a written consent form from where he/she will sign before participating in the study.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 Background information and level of awareness

A total of 130 participants from Kiyindi landing site were included in the study; 80 males and 50 females. The majority of the participants (53.1%) were between 19 and 35 years and very few (2.3%) of the participants were 65 years and above (Table 1).

Table 1: Showing background information and level of awareness of bilharzia among study participants from the different fishing communities in Buikwe district.

Characteristic	n (%)	Characteristic	n (%)
Sex		Education level	
Female	50(38.5)	No formal schooling	29(22.3)
Male	80(61.5)	Incomplete primary	33(25.4)
Age group		Completed primary	21(16.2)
7-18	23(17.7)	Incomplete secondary	39(30.0)
19-35	69(53.1)	Completed secondary	5(3.8)
36-65	35(26.9)	Post-secondary	1(0.8)
65+	3(2.3)	Graduate and above	2(1.5)
Source of information			
Community	97(74.6)	Lake shore activities	
Media	3(2.3)	Fishing	20 (15.4)
Health centre	10(7.7)	Fetching water	13(10.0)
Other	15(11.5)	Washing clothes	7(5.4)
Never heard	5(3.8)	Selling fish	28(21.5)
Heard of bilharzia		Agriculture	2(1.5)
Yes	125(96.2)	Other businesses e.g. selling boat fuel	60(46.2)
No	5(3.8)		
Time spent at the lake			
1-3 hours	49(37.7)		
3-5 hours	10(7.7)		
More than 5 hours	71(54.6)		

Young participants were in the age group 7-18 years (17.7%), whereas the rest of the adults were represented in age group of 36-65 years. A big number (29%) of the respondents had no formal education. Of the remaining 71% who had attained formal education, 16.2% and 5% completed primary and secondary school, respectively (Table 1). The number of graduates was very small (1.5%). Common activities carried out at Kiyindi landing site are fishing (15.4%) and selling of fish (21.5%); other activities included fetching water (10%) and washing of clothes (5.4%), and a few (1.5%) practiced agriculture, and 60/130 (46.2%) were business men and women; involved in selling boat fuel, boat engines, carpentry, hair dressing and food retailing. Respondents who spent approximately 1-3 hours at the lake or the lake shore every day constitute 37.7%, 7.7% spent 3-5 hours, and the remaining 54.6% spent more than 5 hours as shown in table 1 above. The majority of the respondents (96.2%; 125/130) had heard of and aware of the existence of bilharzia in Buikwe district where as a few (3.8%; 5/130) had not heard of it. Of the 125 respondents, 97 heard it from the community, 3 from media, 10 from the health care centre and 15 from any other sources of information (school, neighboring landing sites) as shown in table 1 above.

4.2 Level of awareness of transmission of bilharzia in Buikwe district

A small percentage of 2.3% of the respondents agreed that transmission is only through sexual intercourse; a percentage of 3.8% thought that drinking un boiled water was the only transmission route of bilharzia; a similar percentage 3.8% of the respondents, agreed that eating un cooked food was the only possible transmission route; 6.9% of the respondents consented to witch craft being the possible transmission route; ; and 6.9% of respondents did not know any transmission routes of bilharzia; 21.5% adhered to contact with lake water through fishing, swimming, washing, bathing and playing to be the only possible transmission route; a percentage of 54.6% of the respondents agreed to other possible transmission routes of bilharzia in addition to the ones which were listed in the questionnaire (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: A pie chart showing level of awareness of transmission of bilharzia in Buikwe district

4.3: Level of awareness of the symptoms of bilharzia in Buikwe district

Symptoms	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
ABDOMINAL PAINS AND SWEELINGS	12	9.2
DIARRHEA	2	1.5
PERSISTENT COUGH AND SHORT BREATH	1	0.8
SKIN RASH	1	0.8
OTHER	85	65.4
DONT KNOW	29	22.3
Total	130	100.0

Amongst the respondents, 0.8% suggested that skin rash was the only symptom of bilharzia; 0.8% of the respondents suggested persistent cough and short breath as the only symptom; 1.5%

respondents who agreed that diarrhea was a symptom; 9.2% agreed that abdominal pains and swellings are the only symptoms of bilharzia, 22.3% respondents who did not know any symptom(s) and a percentage of 65.4% of the respondents suggested other symptoms as shown in table 2 above.

4.4 Level of awareness of preventive measures of bilharzia in Buikwe district.

Table 3: Different preventive measures of bilharzia practiced by participants in Kiyindi fishing community, Buikwe district		
Control Measures	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
BILHARZIA IMMUNISATION OR VACCINATION	8	6.2
AVOID PEDALING, SWIMMING AND WASHING IN FRESH WATER	11	8.5
BOIL OR FILTER WATER BEFORE DRINKING	4	3.1
SEEK MEDICAL ATTENTION IMMEDIATELY IN CASE OF EXPOSURE	5	3.8
OTHER	89	68.4
DONT KNOW	13	10.0
Total	130	100.0

A small percentage of 3.1% suggested that boiling or filtering water before drinking would prevent bilharzia infection; 3.8% of the respondents agreed that seeking medical attention immediately in case of exposure to the infection would prevent further spread of bilharzia; 6.2% of the respondents consented that immunization or vaccination of bilharzia could curb the spread of the infection; 8.5% of the respondents suggested that avoiding pedaling, swimming and washing in fresh water could prevent the spread of bilharzia; 10% of the respondents did not suggest any preventive measures of the infection and a large percentage of 68.4% suggested other preventive measures of bilharzia in addition to those which were listed in the questionnaire as seen in table 3 above.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.1 DISCUSSION

The majority of the participants (96.2 %) had heard of bilharzia infection and aware of the disease, probably because they live in a bilharzia endemic region. This can also be attributed to the sensitization campaigns carried out by community leaders and village health workers, the media over radios, the government (Ministry of Health) and Non-Governmental Organizations, in the bilharzia endemic areas. Although many of them were aware of bilharzia in their communities, very few of them were aware of how bilharzia is transmitted; only 21.5% knew that bilharzia infection is through contact with contaminated water.

The female to male ratio 38.5/61.5 shows that most economic activities at the Lake shoreline of Buikwe district were carried out by the men; for example, fishing, fetching water, carrying passengers on boats, carpentry and selling fish among others. Over 50% of the respondents were of the age group 19-35 years and this explains why the highest population at the landing site comprised of youths who were energetic enough to carry out work at the lake shore. The women were mainly involved in activities like washing cloths and agriculture. Such activities which involve contact with water put the communities at the risk of being infected with bilharzia; this study shows that about 62.3% spend more than three hours at the lake shore; which exposes them to bilharzia infection.

Only 11.5% of the study participants were aware of the symptoms shown by a person infected with bilharzia; these included abdominal pain, enlargement of the stomach, skin rash and diarrhea. The remaining 88.5% of the participants either did not know or thought there are other symptoms not described in the questionnaire. The study further shows that 39.2% of the participants were not aware of how bilharzia is controlled and about 13.9% sought for local healers' advice or used herbs. The rest of the participants were aware that bilharzia infections can be controlled by using praziquantel and seeking for medical advice from health workers. This can be attributed to lack of education because the study shows that majority of the participants (77.7%) never had any formal education, and others neither completed primary nor secondary education. Much of the information (74.65%) that they knew about bilharzia was from the community, from fellow villagers who could have been equally ignorant. Probably,

this explains why some of the participants thought that bilharzia transmission is by witchcraft, through sexual intercourse or eating uncooked food.

In conclusion, our findings show that the youth (19-35 years) are the most informed group of participants about bilharzia at Kiyindi Lake Victoria landing site in Buikwe district. Although the government as well as schools have contributed a lot sensitizing endemic communities about bilharzia, this study shows that, many community members need more education concerning the transmission and control of infection. There is still need for epidemiological studies to counteract the continued poor sanitation at the Lake shoreline.

From our study, we recommend the following;

- i. Increase funding and action by constructing many free accessible public latrines
- ii. Law enforcement by community leaders on proper sanitation habits
- iii. Construction of permanent health care centres and recruitment of professional skilled health workers by the government
- iv. Increase money in fields of research in order to allow creation of vaccine for bilharzia, and even effect price cuts or reductions on praziquantel tablets on the market.
- v. Encouraging and availing protective gears to the fishermen and these should be supplied to the community people regularly and promptly.
- vi. Enforcing adult education from which the elderly people acquire knowledge and skills on basic health practices

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: CONSENT FORM

You are kindly requested to take part in a research study conducted by Bweete Paul, Lule Frank Adrian, Nakanya Victoria and Obbo Demba Jude, Bachelor of Science with education students at the College of education and external studies, Makerere University. Results from this study will contribute to the students' study report as well as control of bilharzia at this landing site. Because you meet requirements for participation in this study, you were selected as a possible participant.

I. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

The study is intended to establish the level of awareness, attitude and preventive measure of intestinal schistosomiasis. The study also aims at creating awareness to the fishing communities about intestinal schistosomiasis especially those who are unfamiliar with the infection.

II. STUDY PROCEDURE

If you volunteer to participate in this study, we would ask you to complete the questionnaire that will require about 15-20 minutes of your time and kindly be honest.

III. RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

You may feel uncomfortable talking about intestinal schistosomiasis. Time taken may cause a discomfort to some of you. You may also refuse to answer any part of the questionnaire at any time.

IV. COMPENSATION

You will not pay nor be paid to participate in this research study.

V. BENEFITS

Taking part in this interview has no personal benefit for you. Your participation will help us to find more about intestinal schistosomiasis and its preventive measures among the fishing community. This will help to improve the control of bilharzia in future. Your responses will enable the researchers attain information about the level of awareness of bilharzia

VI. CONFIDENTIALITY

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential. The only place your name will be written down is on this informed consent form. All information you provide will be kept in a locked file and your name will never be used in research reports.

VII. PARTICIPATION AND FREEDOM TO WITHDRAW FROM THE STUDY

You may choose to be in this research study or not, if you volunteer to be in this study, you may withdraw at any time. You may also refuse to answer any question you don't want to answer. The investigator may withdraw you from this research if circumstances arise which warrant doing so.

VIII. SIGNATURE OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANT

The information above was described to me by Bweete Paul, Lule Frank Adrian, Nakamya Victoria and Obbo Demba Jude and was satisfactorily translated to me. I was given opportunity to ask questions and these questions were answered to my satisfaction. I hereby consent voluntarily to participate in the study.

Participant: Signatureand Date.....

IX. SIGNATURE OF RESEARCHERS

We declare that we explained the information in this document to the participant.

He/she was encouraged and given ample time to ask us any questions.

Students' Names	Signature.
1.
2.
3.
4.

Date:

APPENDIX 2: THE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear respondent, this study is aimed at establishing the level of awareness about bilharzia in the fishing community of Kiyindi Landing Site, Buikwe District. You are kindly requested to respond to the following questions as honestly as possible. The information that you will give will be treated with utmost confidentiality and used safely for the purpose of this research only.

Please tick the most appropriate answers and where need be write in the spaces provided.

Social demographics

Sex male female

Age group

07-18 years 19-35years 36-65years 65+

Highest level of education attained

- No formal schooling
- Incomplete primary school
- Completed primary
- Incomplete secondary school
- Completed secondary school
- Post-secondary e.g. certificate and diploma program
- Graduate and above

Which activity do carryout in the lake or at the lakeshore?

- fishing
- Fetching water

Washing clothes

Selling fish

Agriculture

If yes, how much time do you spend the lake or lake shore every day?

1-3 hours

3-5 hours

More than 5 hours

Have you heard of bilharzia infection before?

YES

NO

If yes, where did you hear it from?

Community e.g. fishermen

Media

Health care centre

Any other.....

What are the possible transmission routes of bilharzia?

Witchcraft

Through sexual intercourse with an infected person

Contact with lake water e.g. through fishing, swimming, washing, bathing, and playing in the lake

Drinking unboiled water

Eating uncooked foods

Walking bare footed

Any other.....

Have you or any member of your household suffered from bilharzia?

Yes

No

If yes which of the following symptoms did you have or they had?

Abdominal pains and swellings

Diarrhea

Blood in stool

Persistent cough and short breath

Skin rash

High temperature fever

Any other.....

Which parts of the body do you think are affected by bilharzia?

Skin

Liver

Kidney

Stomach

Urinary tract

The heart

Any other.....

What did you do when you realized you were suffering from bilharzia?

Sought advice from local healer

Herbal medicine

Visited health centre immediately

Taking praziquantel tablets

Did not take any measures

Any other.....

How do you think you can prevent bilharzia?

Bilharzia immunization or vaccination

Avoid pedaling, swimming and washing in fresh water

Boil or filter water before drinking

Seek medical attention immediately in case of any exposure to the lake

Apply skin repellants or towel to dry the skin immediately after contact with lake water

Any other.....

Have your community leaders and health workers tried to sensitize about bilharzia infection?

Yes

No

If yes, identify some of the activities organized by community to increase awareness and control?

Posters and flyers

Discussion about bilharzia infection in schools

Sensitization campaigns for the community around the lake

Health campaigns about the disease

Mass drug administration campaigns

Any other.....

THANK YOU, DEAR RESPONDENT